

The reconfirmation of the presence of unknown human pathogenic coronavirus in post vaccinated case

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Summary: In the publication from November 2021, there was a report of presence of unknown human pathogenic coronavirus in post vaccinated case from the city Duisburg in Germany. The gene sequencing was not possible for these samples because of wobble primers being used during the conventional PCR test, therefore a new test was done. This case is now reconfirmed through another coronavirus genera specific conventional PCR in gel agarose.

Keywords: SARS CoV-2, Coronavirus, Virology, PCR, Vaccine

Introduction: There are several reports about the mutations infecting vaccinated persons during pandemic outbreak of SARS CoV-2. But we reported the first case of unknown coronavirus in a post vaccinated case in November 21 as the samples of a patient were negative for several human coronaviruses as well as other respiratory pathogens, but they were only positive in one conventional PCR according to the method from Moes et al. 2005. (Bhatia 2021)

Now these samples were being investigated further whether other coronavirus genera PCR test tests can detect this unknown virus.

Methods: The isolated RNA samples were tested according to method described in the recent research work from Holbrook et al. 2021. The RNA was converted into cDNA, which was tested in semi nested PCR. The PCR products were run in gel agarose to visualize the specific bands. The positive and negative controls were added during the PCR test. The test was repeated at least 3 times to confirm the results.

Results: The results of gel agarose are showing the presence of specific bands as shown in Picture 1. The tests were done more than 3 times and found that each time, it produced the specific band for coronavirus genera. This test also generated the correct bands in positive controls, while there were no bands in negative controls.

Discussion: In the previous publication, the samples were shown to be positive in pancorona PCR test, but the gene sequencing was not possible as there were wobble primers being used during the PCR. (Vijgen et al. 2008) The samples were subjected to another conventional PCR test for detecting the presence of coronavirus genera as described in the recent publication from Holbrook et al 2021. This test generated a highly specific band. This test reconfirms the presence of a human coronavirus, which was not detected with different specific tests for SARS CoV, SARS CoV-2, MERS, OC43, NL63, 229E and HKU1 with real time PCR. Both tests from Moes and Holbrook are indicating that this is unknown human coronavirus, which has infected a person after the vaccination and causes symptoms like coughing, itching in throat and running nose. The proposed name of this coronavirus is Bhatia coronavirus to make scientific discussions easier. (Bhatia 2021) There are no bands in negative controls, which indicate also that there is no cross reaction or cross contamination during the testing.

It was found that test from Holbrook et al. functions well with cDNA because the attempts to do one step PCR directly from RNA failed at the beginning. (Data not shown)

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Picture 1 is showing the presence of specific bands for coronavirus genera in two different PCR tests in gel agarose.